

1 **Inert liquid exfoliation and Langmuir-type thin film processing of semi metallic metal**
2 **diborides.**

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1 **Abstract:**

2 Graphite is one of only a few layered materials that can be exfoliated into nanosheets with semi-
3 metallic properties, which limits the applications of nanosheet-based electrodes to material
4 combinations compatible with the work function of graphene. It is therefore important to
5 identify additional metallic or semi-metallic 2D nanomaterials that can be processed in solution
6 for scalable fabrication of printed electronic devices. Metal diborides represent a family of
7 layered non-van der Waals crystals with semi-metallic properties for all nanosheet thicknesses.
8 While previous reports show that the exfoliated nanomaterial is prone to oxidation, we
9 demonstrate a readily accessible inert exfoliation process to produce quasi 2D nanoplatelets
10 with intrinsic material properties. For this purpose, we demonstrate the exfoliation of three
11 representative metal diborides (MgB_2 , CrB_2 and ZrB_2) under inert conditions. Nanomaterial is
12 characterised using a combination of TEM, SEM, AFM, IR, and UV-Vis measurements, with
13 only minimal oxidation indicated post-processing. By depositing the pristine metal diboride
14 nanoplatelets as thin-films using a Langmuir-type deposition technique, the ohmic behaviour
15 of the networks is validated. Furthermore, the material decomposition is studied using a
16 combination of electrical and optical measurements after controlled exposure to ambient
17 conditions. Finally, we report an efficient, low-cost approach for sample encapsulation to
18 protect the deposited nanomaterials from oxidation. This is used to demonstrate low-gauge
19 factor strain sensors, confirming metal diboride nanosheets as a suitable alternative to graphene
20 for electrode materials in printed electronics.

21 **Keywords:** Magnesium Diboride, Liquid/Liquid Interface Deposition, Morphology Control,
22 Thin Films, 2D Nanomaterials, Inert Exfoliation, Liquid Phase Exfoliation, Nanomaterial
23 Stability

24

25 **Introduction:**

26 In recent years, liquid exfoliated 2D materials have become important for a range of
27 applications in areas from printed electronics^[1-4] to sensing^[5-8] to energy storage^[9-12]. In the
28 former area, many researchers have commented that the family of 2D materials is particularly
29 important as it includes conducting, semiconducting and insulating members^[3, 13] and so can
30 contribute all the building blocks of electronic devices. Indeed, various researchers have
31 reported all-2D printed electronic devices where electrodes, dielectric and channel material are
32 fabricated from different 2D materials.^[1, 3] However, while there are many semiconducting 2D
33 materials that can be liquid exfoliated and solution processed, there are significantly fewer
34 insulating and conducting ones. In the latter category, the main materials are graphene,^[14]
35 MXenes,^[15] conducting metal chalcogenides (*e.g.*, 1T MoS_2)^[16, 17] and silver nanoplatelets.^[18]
36 Of these, the most common material, graphene, yields solution processed films which are not

1 particularly conductive, generally 10^3 - 10^5 S/m.^[19-23] Thus, it would be advantageous to increase
2 the number of solution processable, conducting 2D materials.

3 Layered metal diborides form a family of layered non-van der Waals semi-metallic ceramics
4 comprised of bivalent metal ions sandwiched by negatively charged boron sheets with a general
5 stoichiometry of MB_2 ($M = Al^{2+}, Mg^{2+}, Cr^{2+}, Hf^{2+}, Nb^{2+}, Ta^{2+}, Ti^{2+}, V^{2+}, Zr^{2+}$). All layered
6 metal diborides crystallise in a hexagonal structure (space group $P6/mmm$), as schematically
7 shown in Figure 1A.^[24, 25] The semi-metallic behaviour of many members of this family results
8 from dispersive nature of the energy bands over the whole Brillouin zone with only few orbitals
9 crossing the Fermi level.^[26, 27] At room temperature, the resistivity of polycrystalline bulk MgB_2
10 is $\rho \sim 1-10 \times 10^{-7} \Omega m$ ($\sigma \sim 0.1-1 \times 10^7$ S/m) and $dp/dT > 0$, consistent with metal-like behaviour.^{[28,}
11 ^{29]} We note that MgB_2 undergoes a transition to superconducting behaviour at 39K.^[29, 30]

12 The electronic structure of MgB_2 is intriguing due to its similarity to graphite. It features three
13 bonding σ -bands from sp^2 hybridization within the boron layer and a pair of π -bands from p_z -
14 orbital hybridization. The strong in-plane electron dispersion arises from efficient p-orbital
15 overlap between neighbouring boron atoms, while interlayer overlap (especially p_{xy} -orbitals)
16 results in a small k_z -dispersion (< 1 eV). This leads to two cylindrical sheets around the Γ -A-
17 line on the Fermi surface. The distinctive covalent character of unoccupied Γ states with p_{xy}
18 symmetry crossing the Fermi level has been studied in theory and experimentally using charge
19 density experiments, revealing its impact on transport characteristics and superconductivity,
20 while also indicating structural instabilities.^[26, 27]

21 In concise terms, this implies that the bonding nature between boron atoms in a metal diboride
22 is considered covalent, while the interlayer bonding with ionized magnesium atoms possesses
23 metallic attributes with delocalized electrons in the interstitial spaces.^[27] This stands in contrast
24 to graphite, where covalent bonding within the carbon lattice is saturated, and the "cylindrical"
25 sheets in the Fermi surface originate from π -bands with more two-dimensional character
26 compared to the bands formed in metal diborides.^[31] This distinction holds significance as it
27 results in interactions which are strong in the in-plane directions and reasonably strong in the
28 out-of-plane direction for metal diborides. In contrast, the out-of-plane attraction in graphite
29 relies solely on van der Waals interactions, leading to a significant anisotropy in binding
30 strength between in-plane and out-of-plane directions. This distinction facilitates efficient
31 exfoliation of graphite into reasonably high aspect ratio two-dimensional (2D) nanosheets.^[32]
32 The binding strength anisotropy is expected to be considerably lower for metal diborides.

33 Upon exfoliation, a less pronounced anisotropy of the binding energy is expected to result in
34 nanosheets with a lower length/thickness aspect ratio.^[32] However, despite some reports on
35 their sonication assisted exfoliation in liquid media,^[25, 33-39] only little quantitative information
36 can be found in the literature on the attainable nanosheet dimensions of liquid exfoliated metal
37 diborides, or how the exfoliation influences their electronic properties. Furthermore, prior

1 studies suggest that the nanomaterial is susceptible to surface functionalisation by oxide and
2 hydroxide species when exposed to ambient or aqueous environments (see SI, Section 7 for an
3 additional discussion and a comparison of results published in the literature).^[25, 33-42]

4 In this study, we provide first quantitative insights on size, electronic properties and reactivity
5 of pristine sonication assisted liquid phase exfoliated metal diborides. MgB₂ powder is
6 exfoliated in dry and degassed isopropanol, and the nanomaterials' sensitivity to ambient
7 oxygen is studied by comparing exfoliation under ambient and inert conditions. To remove
8 unexfoliated material, as well as oxidized material and impurities, nanosheet dispersions
9 undergo two centrifugation steps, as described in more detail in the methods section. Statistical
10 analysis of nanoplatelet size and thickness is conducted through SEM and AFM measurements.
11 Characterization includes UV-Vis measurements, EDX spectroscopy, and IR transmittance,
12 indicating significant oxidation for ambient-exfoliated samples. Nanoplatelets produced under
13 inert conditions are further analysed via TEM, confirming crystallinity. We further employ an
14 inert Langmuir-type deposition for fabrication of thin films with high, metallic conductivity.
15 Nanosheet films and inks exposed to ambient conditions show material decomposition over
16 time, demonstrated via decay of optical extinction and electrical conductivity. Half-lives for
17 decomposition provide an upper limit for processing time while encapsulation can be used to
18 stabilize the films.

19

20 **Results/Discussion**

21 **Assessing the impact of ambient oxygen during exfoliation**

22 Prior to the exfoliation, statistical SEM measurements were used to find the distribution of
23 crystallite sizes found in the powdered starting material. These measurements confirm the
24 layered character of the material (Figure 1B), and reveal a broad distribution of crystallite sizes
25 with an average lateral size of ~1 μm (Figure 1C).

26 For material exfoliation, two samples of magnesium diboride nanosheets were prepared by
27 sonication assisted exfoliation in IPA for 7 hours under ambient and inert conditions
28 respectively. Both dispersions were subjected to two centrifugation steps. The first at 200 g is
29 to remove unexfoliated material from the dispersion, and the second step at 3000 g to collect
30 the nanosheets as sediment, leaving any small particles, soluble oxides or impurities in the
31 supernatant. Collecting the nanosheets as sediment allows one to redisperse the nanomaterial
32 in small volumes of fresh solvent at a concentration of choice. All analysis was performed on
33 samples prepared according to this procedure. Resulting inks from both ambient and inert
34 exfoliation conditions were subjected to the same statistical microscopic analysis as the powder
35 (Figure 1D-I). The SEM analysis shows no difference between the nanosheet sizes for the two
36 samples prepared under ambient (Figure 1D-F), and inert (Figure 1G-I) conditions. In both
37 cases, an average lateral nanosheet size of ~350 nm is found by measuring the lateral size of

1 >300 individual nanosheets for both samples. For further characterisation, optical absorbance
2 measurements on both dispersions have been carried out (Figure 2A). While both samples show
3 a broad absorption feature over the entire accessible spectroscopic range, the sample exfoliated
4 in ambient shows an additional peak in the UV-region, which can be attributed to contributions
5 from magnesium oxide.^[43] No such feature is observed for the inert sample, which only shows
6 a weak peak at ~260 nm. We attribute this feature to an optical excitation in pristine MgB₂,
7 which is masked by oxide contributions in the ambient sample. In addition, EDX and IR-
8 transmittance measurements have been performed on both samples, including the starting
9 material as a reference (Figure 2B-C). Both measurements indicate that some oxides are present
10 in the starting material. While no oxide contribution is observed in the spectra for nanosheets
11 exfoliated under inert conditions, significant oxidation is evident in absorbance spectroscopy,
12 EDX and IR transmission after exfoliation in ambient conditions.

13 **Quantitative analysis of the nanomaterial**

14 Due to the strong impact of ambient oxygen on the nanomaterial composition, only inert
15 processed nanosheets were subjected to further analysis. In order to assess the preservation of
16 crystallinity in the exfoliated material, samples were deposited via drop casting under inert
17 conditions and subsequently analysed using TEM, as well as selected-area electron diffraction
18 (SAED) measurements. Bright field TEM imaging shows different sizes of MgB₂ particles
19 (Figure 3A). SAED measurements performed on diverse particles reveal that thicker particles
20 typically exhibit crystalline properties, whereas thinner particles tend to possess amorphous
21 characteristics (Figure 3B; see SI, Figure S1 for additional examples).

22 To gain further insights into the dimensions of the produced MgB₂ nanosheets, atomic force
23 measurements (AFM) were employed to quantitatively analyse the nanosheet size and thickness
24 distributions. For this purpose, diluted ink samples were deposited on Si/SiO₂ substrates, as
25 described in more detail in the SI, and subjected to statistical analysis. An overview AFM image
26 is shown in Figure 3C, presenting nanosheets of similar size and morphology as observed by
27 electron microscopy. As the nanosheet size and thickness distribution of a standard sample is
28 typically very broad, images of the same region have been measured at different resolution to
29 account for pixelation effects. Additionally, reported corrections based on the correlation of
30 comprehensive TEM and AFM statistics on samples analysed using the same type of AFM
31 cantilevers as in this work have been applied to account for tip broadening.

32 In order to convert the measured apparent thickness into nanosheet layer number, factors such
33 as solvent residues, measurement parameters, and distinct interactions between the tip and the
34 nanosheet, or substrate surface, need to be taken into account.^[44-47] Thus, the measured height
35 (t), is proportional but not identical to a multiple of the crystallographic interlayer distance of
36 the nanosheets. To this end, the measured height from AFM can be converted into the nanosheet
37 layer number (N) by careful analysis of step heights of incompletely exfoliated nanosheets.^{[48-}

1 ^{50]} An example of a nanosheet with steps of different layer numbers is shown in Figure 3D. The
2 measured AFM profile across the nanosheet as indicated by the dashed line shows steps with a
3 relative height of a multiple of the apparent AFM monolayer thickness.^[51] Statistical analysis
4 on the step height extracted from many nanosheets reveals the measured step height to cluster
5 in multiples of 0.8 nm (Figure 3E), a value which can be taken as the apparent thickness of the
6 thinnest possible MgB₂ structure, which we term a monolayer, and assume to consist of a
7 combination of individual boron and magnesium layers. Thus, this value can be used to convert
8 the measured height into the number of monolayers per nanosheet (N).

9 The above-mentioned considerations, in combination with careful statistical analysis of large
10 datasets enables us to reliably determine the nanosheet size and thickness distribution. This is
11 a powerful method for further elaboration of theoretic concepts, and subsequent correlation of
12 such to measured nanosheet properties either in dispersion^[9, 52] or in deposited films.^[53] The
13 result of the statistical evaluation of the nanosheet length and thickness for more than 1000
14 individual MgB₂ nanosheets is presented in Figure 3F. This scatterplot of the length, L, versus
15 layer number, N, of individual nanosheets shows that thin nanosheets tend to be small, and vice
16 versa, which is a typical observation for nanomaterials prepared by sonication-assisted liquid
17 phase exfoliation.^[32] Histograms for the nanosheet length (Figure 3G), and layer number
18 (Figure 3H) show the typical lognormal distributions for the nanosheet dimensions. The AFM
19 data for the nanosheet length can be compared to the size information from SEM measurements
20 (Figure 1I). The individual datasets agree reasonably well: an average nanosheet length of
21 $\langle L \rangle_{\text{AFM}} = 349 \pm 11$ nm is found from statistical AFM measurements, and $\langle L \rangle_{\text{SEM}} = 387 \pm 10$ nm
22 has been extracted from SEM. The average nanosheet layer number, $\langle N \rangle$ could only be
23 determined from AFM measurements and is found to be 30 ± 1 layers from statistical analysis.
24 In addition, taking the monolayer thickness as the c-axis lattice parameter (0.35 nm), allows
25 one to calculate the mean nanosheet aspect ratio (length/thickness) to be 12.9. Further, we find
26 a power law relation between the mean nanosheet area and the average layer number consistent
27 to previous reports^[9, 32, 54] (see SI, Figure S2).

28 In further analysis, the yield of the exfoliated material was determined to be 21% of the initial
29 mass by gravimetric weighing of a known volume of filtered nanomaterial. While the yield of
30 the exfoliated material appears low, it should be noted that the fraction removed as unexfoliated
31 material after the first centrifugation step can be used for subsequent exfoliation steps, as
32 demonstrated previously for other material systems.^[14, 55, 56] Knowledge of the nanomaterial
33 yield holds significance for many reasons as it provides quantitative insights into the efficiency
34 of the exfoliation process, aiding process optimization, and hence cost-effectiveness. Therefore,
35 coefficient spectra of exfoliated nanomaterial have been determined for optical extinction, $\epsilon(\lambda)$,
36 and absorbance, $\alpha(\lambda)$, using nanomaterial inks at known concentrations. Additionally, this
37 allows extraction of the wavelength dependent scattering coefficient, $\sigma(\lambda)$ from the relation
38 $\sigma(\lambda) = \epsilon(\lambda) - \alpha(\lambda)$.^[57] The coefficient spectra are shown in Figure 3I, with each showing

1 broad featureless behaviour consistent with the metallic nature of MgB₂. Knowledge of the
2 optical coefficients is valuable as the spectra not only enable fine-tuning of the MgB₂ ink
3 concentration for unknown samples, facilitating swift and reliable standard measurements, but
4 also provide qualitative insights into the nanomaterial size and thickness distribution from the
5 scattering contribution to the extinction spectra.

6 **Deposition of MgB₂ thin films**

7 While the capability of preparing nanomaterials without altering their structure or
8 chemical composition is important, depositing them into thin films with controllable
9 morphology, while preserving their structural integrity holds similar significance. To this end,
10 three different deposition techniques were tested: vacuum filtration, spray coating and a
11 modified Langmuir-Schaefer (LS) deposition, with the expectation that each method yields
12 slightly different film morphology. This allows us to study the influence of morphology on the
13 electrical properties of the films, as well as their impact on the materials' spectroscopic response
14 (*i.e.*, indications for material decomposition). For this purpose, the same spectroscopic methods
15 were applied to the deposited nanomaterial as used for the initial nanosheet characterisation
16 mentioned above. A combination of optical and electron microscopy, EDX and IR spectroscopy
17 as well as I-V measurements are shown and discussed for each deposition technique in the SI
18 (Figure S3). Experimental details are given in the Methods section (see SI). Based on the results
19 from both microscopy and spectroscopy, Langmuir-Schaefer deposited films appear to be more
20 uniform and demonstrate fewer signs of material decomposition, when compared to films
21 fabricated by filtration and spray coating (Figure S3).

22 Consequently, the following discussion will focus on the attributes of nanosheet networks
23 prepared by Langmuir-type deposition. It is worth noting that the modified Langmuir-Schaefer
24 deposition technique employed in this study is currently experimental and will undergo further
25 refinement in the future. In our methodology, the nanomaterial is introduced into a liquid/liquid
26 interface (water/hexane), leading to a reduction in interfacial energy at the injection point. This
27 initiates the self-assembly of a tiled nanomaterial layer at the interface once a sufficient amount
28 of material is introduced. Images captured through optical microscopy and SEM of a transferred
29 self-organized MgB₂ nanosheet layer are presented in Figure 4A-B.

30 In further analysis of the nanosheet networks, EDX spectra were acquired on LS films of the
31 deposited nanosheets. The data is shown in comparison to measurements on freshly exfoliated
32 nanosheets drop cast in an argon atmosphere (Figure 4C). According to the EDX
33 measurements, only slight oxidation of the material occurred during the LS deposition process,
34 suggesting a ratio of Mg:B:O of 1:2:0.8. While care should be taken about the suggested
35 stoichiometry determined by EDX spectroscopy, qualitative trends can be used to compare the
36 oxygen content in fabricated samples. To this end, EDX and IR spectra have been acquired on
37 samples after filtration, spray coating, and Langmuir-deposition. Spectra acquired on filtered

1 and sprayed nanosheets are shown in the SI (see Figure S3). The measurements suggest that
2 less oxygen was introduced in the LS-deposited films compared to filtered (EDX Mg:B:O ratio
3 of 1:1.5:2.7) or spray deposited (1:2.8:1.1) nanosheets. For additional results, and a detailed
4 discussion, see SI, section 3.

5 In order to study crystallinity and any potential preferred orientation effects in the deposited
6 nanomaterial, a Langmuir-type deposition was performed on a TEM grid and subjected to
7 SAED measurements (Figure 4D-E). The sample displays homogenous coverage with sparser
8 regions close to holes in the grid. Nanosheets exhibit edge-to-edge orientation, with some edges
9 partially overlapping (Figure 4E). SAED measurements on an individual nanosheet
10 demonstrate that the crystallinity is not affected during the deposition steps (Figure 4E, inset).
11 However, no indication on any preferential orientation of the nanosheets within the network is
12 discernible (see SI, Figure S1G-H for additional data).

13 While microscopy indicates a uniform distribution of the nanomaterial on both the micro- and
14 mesoscales, it would be useful to quantify the homogeneity of the nanomaterial coverage across
15 the entire substrate. This can be assessed through spatially resolved transmission scanning. To
16 achieve this, a MgB₂ network deposited onto a glass substrate was subjected to transmission
17 scanning (pixel size ~5 μm). The scanner response was converted into extinction, as elaborated
18 in more detail in the Methods section. The results are presented in the form of an extinction
19 histogram (Figure 4F), displaying a Gaussian bell shape. We assess the sample homogeneity
20 via the coefficient of variation (ratio of standard deviation to the mean). For the distribution
21 histogram in Figure 4F, a coefficient of variation of 0.05 is found, which signifies that the
22 standard deviation of the thickness distribution is 5% of the mean thickness. The thickness and
23 morphology of the deposited nanosheet network is hence considered as homogenous across the
24 entire substrate, when probed at a length scale of ~5 μm.

25 To test the electrical conductivity of the LS-type deposited nanosheets, gold electrodes were
26 deposited on top of an MgB₂ nanosheet network in a transmission line geometry. Contact pads
27 were reinforced with silver paint to provide better contact with the needle probes (see inset
28 Figure 4G). The average I-V curves measured for an array of different electrode spacings are
29 shown in Figure 4G. Ohmic behaviour is observed for all measurements on the Langmuir-type
30 film, indicating that the nanosheets retain their semi-metallic character after exfoliation and
31 deposition. Crucially, this is not the case for networks deposited by filtration (see SI, Figure
32 S3M), or spray coating (see SI, Figure S3N), or for LS-type samples after exposure to ambient
33 conditions (see SI, Figure S4). The network resistance was measured for each electrode
34 separation, and is plotted versus channel length, L , in Figure 4H. The distribution of resistance
35 values is indicated by red dots in Figure 4H, corresponding to individual I-V measurements.
36 The mean resistance for each channel length is given by black circles, with error bars
37 representing the standard deviation. A linear relationship is found consistent with $R = 2R_c +$
38 $L/(\sigma Wt)$, where R_c is the contact resistance, $W = 2.4$ mm is the channel width and $t = 570$ nm

1 is the film thickness. Fitting shows the film conductivity to be $\sigma = (9.5 \pm 1.3) \times 10^4$ S/m and gives
2 a contact resistance of $R_C = 0.7 \Omega$ ($R_C W = 1.7 \Omega \text{ m}$). This conductivity is quite high for solution
3 processed nanosheet networks and is competitive with the state-of-the-art for printed graphene
4 films ($\sim 10^5$ S/m).^[19-23] However, it is somewhat below reported conductivities for MXene films
5 ($\sim 10^6$ S/m)^[58] owing to the far lower aspect ratio of the diboride nanosheets,^[19] and lower than
6 and networks of metallic nanoplatelets ($\sim 10^7$ S/m)^[59] which, following sintering and filament
7 formation, are not separated by a van der Waals gap.

8 Since linear I-V curves can also be indicative of bulk-limited semiconducting channels, we
9 performed transistor measurements to further confirm the semi-metallic behaviour of the MgB_2
10 network. An electrolytically gated thin-film transistor was fabricated from a four-times
11 deposited MgB_2 nanosheet network in a displaced-gate electrode geometry, where an ionic
12 liquid connects the channel to the gate (see SI, Methods section for further details). A gate bias
13 causes the ions to separate and form a double layer on the gate electrode and also throughout
14 the internal surface area of the nanosheet network. For a semiconducting network, this causes
15 an increase in the current density as carriers fill the network to balance the ionic charge.
16 However, there is no current modulation observed in the transfer characteristic in Figure 4I,
17 which is further confirmation of the semi-metallic electrical properties of these networks.

18

19 **Stability of the nanomaterial**

20 As preliminary measurements strongly suggest that the nanomaterial is prone to degradation in
21 ambient conditions, the stability of the nanosheets exfoliated in inert conditions was studied
22 both in the dispersion and after the Langmuir-type deposition to form a film. In the supporting
23 information, we report on preliminary experiments to demonstrate the build-up of Langmuir-
24 type multilayers using multiple iterations of the deposition process to increase the film thickness
25 (see SI, Figure S5). For the purpose of optical measurements on metal diboride thin films, four
26 iterations of the Langmuir Schaefer deposition have been used on optical glass to increase film
27 thickness for a better signal to noise ratio.

28 Samples were exposed to ambient conditions after preparation and extinction spectra were
29 acquired as a function of exposure time, ranging from 0 h to ~ 100 h. For the deposited thin
30 films, additional changes in the I-V characteristics were recorded over time. The results from
31 the photospectroscopic measurements are shown in Figure 5A-B for the nanosheet dispersion
32 and a thin film, respectively. In both cases, systematic changes are observed as a function of
33 exposure time to ambient conditions. The dispersion (Figure 5A) shows a steady change over
34 the entire accessible spectroscopic response. In addition, the initial peak at ~ 220 nm undergoes
35 a systematic change, in line with an electronic contribution that can be assigned to oxidised
36 magnesium species, and a progressive evolution of a water peak at ~ 1450 nm. The latter
37 demonstrates the initial absence of water in the solvent, and how the solvent acquires ambient

1 water over time. The change in the peak at 220 nm, as well as the decrease of the overall optical
2 density can be attributed to oxidation of the nanomaterial. We can rule out effects from
3 aggregation and sedimentation of the nanomaterial as the dispersions were refreshed by
4 sonication prior to each measurement, and no increase of the scattering contribution is observed
5 in the extinction spectra over time.

6 The Langmuir Schaefer deposited nanosheet film (Figure 5B) shows similar time-dependent
7 changes in the photospectroscopic profile to the dispersion. However, the changes to the peak
8 in the UV-region are more pronounced in the film compared to the ink. We presume that this is
9 because of direct exposure of the film to ambient conditions while the nanosheets in dispersion
10 are embedded in a solvent matrix, slowing down the degradation to the diffusion limit.

11 However, such behaviour should be evident from kinetic analysis of the spectra. For this
12 purpose, time dependent changes to the spectra were plotted according to a first (Figure 5C),
13 and a second order (Figure 5D) rate law. Here, the change of the initial MgB₂ concentration is
14 represented by the extinction at 1000 nm, which is solely attributed to the electronic response
15 of the nanomaterial.

16 When plotted as natural logarithm of the optical density versus time, in line with a first order
17 rate law (Figure 5C), the data acquired for the dispersion follows a linear trend, as expected for
18 a diffusion limited decomposition reaction. This is in contrast to the spectra of the deposited
19 film, where no linearization is observed. In contrast, when plotted as inverse optical density
20 over time (Figure 5D), the thin-film data is linear, supporting a second order rate law for the
21 decomposition of the deposited nanomaterial. However, while additional data was collected on
22 other metal diborides (CrB₂ and ZrB₂) the observed trends do not allow an unambiguous rate
23 analysis of the decomposition chemistry. Further details are given in section 6 of the SI. For
24 further analysis, we present an empirical fit to a single exponential function
25 ($\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 + \varepsilon_1 \exp \left[\frac{\ln(2)}{t_{1/2}} \cdot t \right]$), which enables one to estimate the portion of reacted (PoR) material
26 from the amplitude as $PoR = \varepsilon_1 / (\varepsilon_0 + \varepsilon_1)$ (Figure 5E). Approximating the data from the UV
27 Vis measurements on a LS-deposited MgB₂ nanosheet film to infinite timescales suggests that
28 54±1% of the nanomaterial decomposes with an estimated macroscopic nanomaterial half-life
29 of 18±5 h for storage in ambient conditions.”

30 The data from spectrophotometric measurements already gives reasonable insights into the
31 kinetics of the nanomaterial decomposition, as previously demonstrated on other 2D
32 nanomaterial systems.^[9, 49, 60, 61] However, it is expected that the decomposition also has an
33 impact on the physical properties of the nanosheets, such as their conductivity. It was not
34 possible to correlate conductivity measurements with optical measurements taken on the
35 nanosheet dispersion, despite the attempt to deposit nanomaterial from similarly aged
36 dispersions, as the amount of material was insufficient. However, it was possible to measure
37 changes to the conductivity on deposited nanosheet networks over time.

1 While ohmic transport is observed for multiple depositions (see SI, Figure S6), we note that
2 care must be taken when moving a previously deposited nanosheet network through the water
3 surface as material may be washed off due to the high surface tension (see Methods section for
4 additional details).

5 To further study the nanomaterial decomposition upon exposure to ambient conditions, the I-V
6 characteristics of Langmuir Schaefer films after a single, and after four iterative depositions
7 were acquired over time (Figure 5F-G). In both cases, the curves show a systematic change
8 from initially Ohmic to non-Ohmic transport characteristics, in line with progressing material
9 oxidation. Note that the electric measurements were taken on the same films as used for
10 studying the photospectroscopic response over time, as discussed above. This allows us to
11 correlate the conductivity change with the change of the optical characteristics over time.

12 Increasing the film thickness through the adapted Langmuir-type deposition did not lead to an
13 increase in the film conductivity in case of MgB_2 nanosheets (Figure 5H). We attribute this
14 phenomenon to the air sensitivity of the nanomaterial and the increased exposure to ambient
15 oxygen with each repetition of the deposition process for augmenting the film thickness.

16 In further analysis, we plot the evolution of the conductivity (black squares) and optical
17 extinction at 1000 nm (blue circles) of a MgB_2 nanosheet network formed by 4 successive
18 Langmuir-type depositions over time (Figure 6A). Both datasets can be fit to the same
19 exponential decay as described above. However, the data acquired from conductivity
20 measurements imply an even more severe material oxidation ($\text{PoR} = 71 \pm 1\%$) with a half-life of
21 14.2 ± 0.9 h.

22 In addition to studying the decomposition of MgB_2 nanosheets, similar experiments have been
23 reproduced for CrB_2 and ZrB_2 . It is evident from the data that the other metal diborides show a
24 comparable behaviour upon exposure to ambient environment (for further details see SI,
25 Figure S7-S9). The conductivity of all three materials exfoliated under inert conditions and
26 deposited as films using four iterations of the Langmuir-type deposition is shown in Figure 6B.
27 While the conductivity of ZrB_2 is comparable to MgB_2 , the measurements taken on CrB_2
28 Langmuir-type films indicate a $100\times$ lower conductivity.

29 To facilitate a comparison with MgB_2 , extinction and I-V measurements were performed on
30 deposited CrB_2 and ZrB_2 networks as a function of their exposure time to ambient environment
31 (see SI, Figure S10-S11 for further details). All samples show systematic changes to their
32 spectroscopic response. In all cases, the change follows an exponential decay, which can be fit
33 reasonably well to the same equation as used for MgB_2 . This is useful as it allows the
34 nanomaterial's half-life to be extracted (Figure 6C), as well as the portion of reacted material
35 from the amplitude of the fitted exponential. While all materials show significant oxidation over
36 time, the data indicates that a passivation-layer forms based on the portion of reacted material,
37 which is estimated to be between 45-65% for the three materials studied here. Further, the

1 initially ohmic conductivity shows a transition to a more rectifying behaviour as oxidation of
 2 the nanomaterial proceeds and the electrode/material contact evolves (SI, Figure S4 and S11).
 3 The results for all three materials characterised in this work are summarized in Table 1.

4 **Table 1:** Portion of reacted material (PoR) and half-life ($t_{1/2}$) of the nanosheets for both dispersed and deposited
 5 MgB_2 , CrB_2 and ZrB_2 samples. For the thin film samples the PoR and half-life are extracted from both extinction
 6 and network conductivity data.

Material	PoR (dispersion)	PoR (thin film)		$t_{1/2}$ (dispersion)	$t_{1/2}$ (thin film)	
	<i>Extinction</i>	<i>Extinction</i>	<i>Conductivity</i>	<i>Extinction</i>	<i>Extinction</i>	<i>Conductivity</i>
MgB_2	46.9±3.3%	54.4±1.6%	71.0±0.9%	20.8±1.1 h	18±5.0 h	14.2±0.9 h
CrB_2	57.9±4.7%	<i>n.a.</i>	87.4±1.5%	60.4±13.9 h	<i>n.a.</i>	22.1±2.0 h
ZrB_2	64.0±6.3%	77.4±2.2%	92.9±8.2%	127.2±26.6 h	108.0±22.7 h	160.8±25.2 h

7
 8 Due to the sensitivity of metal diboride nanosheets to exposure to ambient conditions, it is
 9 important to develop strategies to protect the nanomaterial from oxidation. While different
 10 approaches have been reported in the past,^[62-64] we demonstrate the use of a spray-on polymer
 11 as an efficient protection layer. The I-V characteristics of a MgB_2 nanosheet thin film were
 12 tested before and after application of the polymer layer, and subsequently measured as a
 13 function of time in ambient conditions for 2 weeks. In the inset of Figure 6D, we show the I-V
 14 curves of the film right before and after the polymer encapsulation. After the deposition of the
 15 polymer layer, a drop in the network conductivity is observed, which we attribute to changes in
 16 the film morphology during the deposition process. Note that after this initial drop, no further
 17 change to the network conductivity is observed over a time-scale of > 300 h (Figure 6D).

18 Within the field of printed flexible electronics, conductive nanomaterials are most commonly
 19 used as an electrode material.^[65] While a high electrical conductivity is prerequisite, it is also
 20 crucial that the electrode conductivity is not significantly affected when the device is strained.
 21 We tested the suitability of our semi-metallic MgB_2 nanosheets for this purpose by performing
 22 piezoresistive measurements on an encapsulated network fabricated by four successive
 23 Langmuir-type depositions on a PET substrate (Figure 6E). Electrical measurements as a
 24 function of strain (ϵ) show only slight changes to the network resistance within the studied
 25 range. The extracted gauge factor ($\Delta R/R_0 = G\epsilon$)^[66] of $G=1.75$, suggests that the network (or
 26 electrode) conductivity remains relatively unperturbed by applied strains. This serves to highlight the
 27 applicability of encapsulated MgB_2 films for use as an electrode material in flexible electronics.

28 29 **Conclusions**

30 In summary, we have demonstrated the exfoliation of three different metal diborides: MgB_2 ,
 31 CrB_2 , and ZnB_2 . The sensitivity of these nanomaterials to ambient oxygen has been highlighted
 32 using the example of MgB_2 , where significant oxidation is observed upon exposure to ambient
 33 conditions, as demonstrated by UV-Vis measurements, IR transmission and EDX spectroscopy.
 34 To address this, a viable and readily accessible method for exfoliating and processing such
 35 materials into thin-films under inert conditions has been demonstrated. The produced

1 nanomaterials have been extensively characterised using a combination of advanced
2 microscopy techniques, including SEM, TEM, and AFM, and statistical analyses to study the
3 nanosheet size- and thickness distributions have been performed.

4 The exfoliated metal diboride nanoplatelets have been deposited into thin films using vacuum
5 filtration, spray coating and a Langmuir-type deposition method, yielding different network
6 morphologies. Promising samples from the Langmuir-type deposition were studied further,
7 including their composition and crystallinity, using IR transmission, UV-Vis, SAED, and EDX
8 spectroscopy, while their electrical characteristics were probed using I-V measurements.
9 Indeed, the Langmuir-type deposited MgB_2 thin films in this work exhibit an unprecedented
10 conductivity of $(9.5 \pm 1.3) \times 10^4$ S/m, and a contact resistance of 0.67Ω if the exposure to oxygen
11 is minimized.

12 As these materials are sensitive to oxygen exposure, we have studied the material
13 decomposition kinetics and quantified the portion of reacted material and macroscopic half-life
14 for nanoplatelets in both the nanomaterial ink and deposited films upon exposure to ambient
15 conditions. This was achieved by tracking changes in the photospectroscopic response and I-V
16 characteristics as a function of exposure time. The results from both yield comparable results
17 and suggest that more than 50% of the nanomaterial decomposes with a half-life of less than
18 one day.

19 Finally, we have demonstrated the metallic character of the deposited metal diboride nanosheet
20 networks using electrical and piezoresistive measurements. MgB_2 films were successfully
21 encapsulated using a spray-on polymer to mitigate oxidation-driven degradation and
22 electromechanically tested. The measured gauge factor of ~ 1.75 for Langmuir-type deposited
23 MgB_2 indicates that the network conductivity is largely invariant within the studied strain range.
24 This highlights the suitability of metal diboride films as electrode materials for flexible
25 electronics.

26

27 **Methods/Experimental**

28 A detailed description of all methods and experiments is given in the supporting information.

1
2 **Figure 1 – SEM comparison of metal diboride nanoplatelets made in ambient, and under**
3 **inert conditions.** (A) Hexagonal AlB_2 type crystal structure, typical for layered metal diborides
4 such as MgB_2 . Layers of negatively charged boron sheets (represented by a green hexagonal
5 lattice) are sandwiched between Mg^{2+} ions (black spheres, square lattice). (B-C) Representative
6 SEM image (B) and size distribution of MgB_2 crystallites (C) in the powder used as starting
7 material. (D) Photograph of the setup used for exfoliation under ambient conditions. (E-F) SEM
8 image showing an overview of drop cast nanosheets after exfoliation (E) using the setup shown
9 in panel D, and corresponding size distribution of MgB_2 nanosheets determined from SEM
10 imaging (F). (G) Photograph of the setup used for exfoliation under inert conditions. (H-I) SEM
11 image showing an overview of drop cast nanosheets after exfoliation (H) using the setup shown
12 in panel G, and corresponding size distribution of MgB_2 nanosheets determined from SEM
13 imaging (I).
14

1
 2 **Figure 2 – Spectroscopic analysis of MgB₂ nanoplatelets prepared under inert conditions.**
 3 (A) Absorbance measurements on nanosheet dispersions made under ambient (red) and inert
 4 conditions (black). An additional peak associated with MgO is found for the ambient.
 5 (B-C) EDX (B) and IR-transmittance (C) measurements for the starting material (grey), and
 6 nanosheets after exfoliation under ambient (red), and inert (black) conditions. The
 7 measurements suggest that both the starting and ambient-exfoliated materials contain oxide
 8 species, which is not evident in the inert exfoliated sample.

9

1
2 **Figure 3 – Quantitative characterization of MgB₂ nanoplatelets prepared under inert**
3 **conditions.** (A) Bright-field TEM image of drop-cast MgB₂ nanoplatelets. A distribution of
4 different sizes is observed, similar to the nanomaterials observed in the SEM. (B) SAED for the
5 triangular particle in (A). The probed region is indicated by the dashed circle and demonstrates
6 reasonable crystallinity of the nanomaterial. (C) Overview AFM image of MgB₂ nanosheets.
7 Particles of a similar size and shape to those seen in the TEM are observed. (D-E) Conversion
8 of apparent AFM height into LPE MgB₂ layer number using line profiles on nanoparticles with
9 suitable steps and terraces. An example is shown in (D) while the statistical analysis of suitable
10 steps is presented in (E). The data are sorted in ascending order, revealing discrete steps of ~0.8
11 nm. (F) Scatter plot of the overall nanosheet size and thickness distribution measured using
12 statistical AFM. The data includes the size and thickness of over 1500 nanoparticles with an
13 average length/thickness aspect ratio of ~12.9. (G-H) Histograms of the lateral nanosheet size
14 (G), and the layer number (H) from statistical analysis of line profiles on individual nanosheets.
15 (I) Optical extinction (black), absorbance (red), and scattering (blue) coefficient spectra for
16 MgB₂ nanoparticles exfoliated under inert conditions.

1
2 **Figure 4: Characterisation of MgB₂ nanoplatelet thin films made by Langmuir-type**
3 **deposition. (A-B)** Optical micrograph (A), and SEM image (B) of a MgB₂ thin film after a
4 single deposition. The sample is homogeneously covered with MgB₂ nanoplatelets. (C) EDX
5 spectra of a deposited thin film (blue) in comparison to the freshly inert exfoliated nanomaterial
6 (black). Note that minimal oxidation is observed after the deposition. (D-E) TEM
7 characterization of Langmuir-type deposited inert MgB₂ on a TEM grid. Nanoparticles are
8 deposited over the entire grid, which sparser regions around the holes in the carbon film (D).
9 Nanosheets show edge-to-edge alignment in the film with partial overlap (E). SAED
10 measurements on an individual nanosheet reveals high crystallinity after the deposition (inset).
11 (F) Extinction histogram from white light transmission scans mapped over a 1×1 cm sample
12 area deposited on quartz glass. The peak is well-described by a single Gaussian distribution
13 (blue line). Note that the single modality is indicative of a homogenous thickness profile across
14 the sample area. (G-H) I-V characteristics (G) and network resistance (H) as a function of
15 channel length, L, for a MgB₂ thin film (average thickness of 570 nm). The sample was
16 characterized using patterned gold top contacts, as shown in the photograph (G, inset). To
17 confirm the homogeneity of the deposited nanomaterial film, all possible electrode
18 combinations have been tested, resulting in an average thin film conductivity of
19 $(9.5 \pm 1.3) \times 10^4$ S/m (F) and a contact resistance of 0.67 Ω. (I) Transfer characteristics of an
20 electrolytically gated MgB₂ thin film transistor after encapsulation, with the gate leakage shown
21 as the dotted line. No charge modulation is observed, demonstrating the metallic characteristics
22 of the nanomaterial.

1
 2 **Figure 5: Nanomaterial stability.** (A-B) Change in the extinction of liquid exfoliated MgB₂
 3 nanoplatelets in dispersion (A) and after thin film deposition on optical glass (B) as a function
 4 of time exposed to ambient conditions. In both cases a systematic decrease in the overall
 5 response is observed for all wavelengths above 450 nm, while the signal below 450 nm
 6 undergoes changes in the spectral profile and shows increased optical density in UV-region,
 7 which is indicative for oxide formation. Further, a peak which can be attributed to water forms
 8 over time in the nanosheet ink. (C-D) Kinetic plots for rate law analysis of the extinction
 9 measurements shown in (A-B). (C) shows the change in the natural logarithm of the optical
 10 density at 1000 nm, and (D) shows the inverse optical density at 1000 nm as a function of time.
 11 While the lines indicate a reasonable agreement with a first order rate law for the dispersed
 12 nanomaterial (C), and a second order rate law for the deposited material (D), the analysis is not
 13 unambiguous, and is discussed in further detail in the SI. (E) Change in the extinction of the
 14 nanosheet ink and thin film at 1000 nm as a function of time. The data can be described by an
 15 empirical exponential fit, which allows determination of the material's half-life. The data for
 16 both individual datasets agrees well and fitting suggests a nanomaterial half-life of 19 ± 1 h, and
 17 18 ± 5 h, for the nanosheet ink and thin film, respectively. (F-G) I-V characteristics as a function
 18 of time for two sets of samples measured after deposition of a single layer (F), and after
 19 deposition of 4 layers (G). In both cases, similar systematic changes are observed: The initial
 20 ohmic response changes to a more rectifying transport behaviour, which is consistent with the
 21 formation of an oxide layer. (H) Conductivity of the same MgB₂ films measured as a function
 22 of the mean film thickness, determined by profilometry at different points across the substrate.
 23 A decrease of the conductivity is observed with increasing film thickness, which is
 24 counterintuitive, and may be attributed to surface oxidation of the nanomaterial during the
 25 processing steps.

1
2 **Figure 6: Material comparison, network encapsulation and electromechanical**
3 **characterisation.** (A) Changes in both the electrical conductivity and optical density at
4 1000 nm of MgB₂ films (from data shown in Figure 5F-G) as a function of storage time in
5 ambient conditions. Both datasets show a similar exponential decay, which implies the two
6 different methods yield a comparable result for the nanomaterial decomposition kinetics. (B-
7 C) Initial conductivity (B) and nanosheet half-life (C) for liquid deposited networks of MgB₂,
8 CrB₂, and ZrB₂ nanosheets. (D) . Evolution of the MgB₂ network conductivity before and after
9 encapsulation. After an initial drop post-encapsulation, which we attribute to changes in the
10 thin film morphology, the conductivity stabilizes for times > 300 h. Inset: I-V curves for a MgB₂
11 nanosheet thin film after 4 iterative Langmuir-type depositions. The green curve was recorded
12 immediately post-deposition. A number of additional curves were recorded at defined time
13 intervals after encapsulation of the film using a spray-on polymer with the red curve
14 corresponding to the first I-V measurement after encapsulation (E) Fractional resistance change
15 of a MgB₂ film as function of applied strain. Inset: Optical photograph of MgB₂ nanosheets
16 deposited on PET after 4 iterations of the Langmuir-type deposition method.

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10

11 **Additional information**

12 Supplementary information is available in the online version of the paper. Correspondence and
13 requests for materials should be addressed to K.S. or J.N.C.

14

15 **Experimental Methods:**

16 Experimental details are given in the Supporting information

17

18 **Supporting Information:**

19 Experimental methods, Additional information on nanomaterial characterisation, Network
20 performance for different deposition techniques, layer by layer deposition, Exfoliation and
21 analysis of CrB₂ and ZrB₂, Degradation kinetics data, literature comparison.

22

23 **Competing financial interests**

24 The authors declare no competing financial interests.

25

26 **References**

- 27 [1] A. G. Kelly, T. Hallam, C. Backes, A. Harvey, A. S. Esmaeily, I. Godwin, J.
28 Coelho, V. Nicolosi, J. Lauth, A. Kulkarni, S. Kinge, L. D. A. Siebbeles, G. S. Duesberg
29 and J. N. Coleman. All-printed thin-film transistors from networks of liquid-exfoliated
30 nanosheets. *Science*, **2017**, 356, 69. DOI: 10.1126/science.aal4062
- 31 [2] X. Chen, X. Wang, Y. Pang, G. Bao, J. Jiang, P. Yang, Y. Chen, T. Rao and W.
32 Liao. Printed Electronics Based on 2D Material Inks: Preparation, Properties, and
33 Applications toward Memristors. *Small Methods*, **2023**, 7, 2201156. DOI:
34 10.1002/smt.202201156
- 35 [3] O. Song, D. Rhee, J. Kim, Y. Jeon, V. Mazánek, A. Söll, Y. A. Kwon, J. H. Cho,
36 Y.-H. Kim, Z. Sofer and J. Kang. All inkjet-printed electronics based on
37 electrochemically exfoliated two-dimensional metal, semiconductor, and dielectric. *npj*
38 *2D Materials and Applications*, **2022**, 6, 64. DOI: 10.1038/s41699-022-00337-1
- 39 [4] S. Conti, L. Pimpolari, G. Calabrese, R. Worsley, S. Majee, D. K. Polyushkin,
40 M. Paur, S. Pace, D. H. Keum, F. Fabbri, G. Iannaccone, M. Macucci, C. Coletti, T.
41 Mueller, C. Casiraghi and G. Fiori. Low-voltage 2D materials-based printed field-effect
42 transistors for integrated digital and analog electronics on paper. *Nature*
43 *Communications*, **2020**, 11, 3566. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-020-17297-z

- 1 [5] K. Lee, B. M. Szydłowska, O. Hartwig, K. Synnatschke, B. Tywoniuk, T.
2 Hartman, T. Tomašević-Ilić, C. P. Gabbett, J. N. Coleman, Z. Sofer, M. Spasenović, C.
3 Backes and G. S. Duesberg. Highly conductive and long-term stable films from liquid-
4 phase exfoliated platinum diselenide. *Journal of Materials Chemistry C*, **2023**, *11*, 593-
5 599. DOI: 10.1039/D2TC03889G
- 6 [6] J. Dai, O. Ogbeide, N. Macadam, Q. Sun, W. Yu, Y. Li, B.-L. Su, T. Hasan, X.
7 Huang and W. Huang. Printed gas sensors. *Chemical Society Reviews*, **2020**, *49*,
8 1756-1789. DOI: 10.1039/C9CS00459A
- 9 [7] X. Sui, S. V. Rangnekar, J. Lee, S. E. Liu, J. R. Downing, L. E. Chaney, X. Yan,
10 H.-J. Jang, H. Pu, X. Shi, S. Zhou, M. C. Hersam and J. Chen. Fully Inkjet-Printed, 2D
11 Materials-Based Field-Effect Transistor for Water Sensing. *Advanced Materials*
12 *Technologies*, **2023**, *8*, 2301288. DOI: 10.1002/admt.202301288
- 13 [8] R. Zhang, J. Jiang and W. Wu. Wearable chemical sensors based on 2D
14 materials for healthcare applications. *Nanoscale*, **2023**, *15*, 3079-3105. DOI:
15 10.1039/D2NR05447G
- 16 [9] K. Synnatschke, J. van Dinter, A. Müller, D. Tiede, L. Spillecke, S. Shao, D.
17 Kelly, J. Konecny, B. Konkena, M. McCrystall, N. Saigal, U. Wurstbauer, W. Bensch,
18 Z. Sofer, J. N. Coleman, R. Klingeler, S. J. Haigh and C. Backes. Exfoliability,
19 magnetism, energy storage and stability of metal thiophosphate nanosheets made in
20 liquid medium. *2D Materials*, **2023**, *10*, 024003. DOI: 10.1088/2053-1583/acba2c
- 21 [10] F. Xie, C. Xu, Y. Song, Q. Liang, J. Ji and S. Wang. 2D-2D heterostructure of
22 ionic liquid-exfoliated MoS₂/MXene as lithium polysulfide barrier for Li-S batteries.
23 *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, **2023**, *636*, 528-536. DOI:
24 10.1016/j.jcis.2023.01.031
- 25 [11] M. R. Islam, S. Afroj and N. Karim. Scalable Production of 2D Material
26 Heterostructure Textiles for High-Performance Wearable Supercapacitors. *ACS Nano*,
27 **2023**, *17*, 18481-18493. DOI: 10.1021/acsnano.3c06181
- 28 [12] A. Panagiotopoulos, G. Nagaraju, S. Tagliaferri, C. Grotta, P. C. Sherrell, M.
29 Sokolikova, G. Cheng, F. Iacoviello, K. Sharda and C. Mattevi. 3D printed inks of two-
30 dimensional semimetallic MoS₂/TiS₂ nanosheets for conductive-additive-free
31 symmetric supercapacitors. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, **2023**, *11*, 16190-16200.
32 DOI: 10.1039/D3TA02508J
- 33 [13] V. Shanmugam, R. A. Mensah, K. Babu, S. Gawusu, A. Chanda, Y. Tu, R. E.
34 Neisiany, M. Försth, G. Sas and O. Das. A Review of the Synthesis, Properties, and
35 Applications of 2D Materials. *Particle & Particle Systems Characterization*, **2022**, *39*,
36 2200031. DOI: 10.1002/ppsc.202200031
- 37 [14] Y. Hernandez, V. Nicolosi, M. Lotya, F. M. Blighe, Z. Sun, S. De, I. T. McGovern,
38 B. Holland, M. Byrne, Y. K. Gun'Ko, J. J. Boland, P. Niraj, G. Duesberg, S.
39 Krishnamurthy, R. Goodhue, J. Hutchison, V. Scardaci, A. C. Ferrari and J. N.
40 Coleman. High-yield production of graphene by liquid-phase exfoliation of graphite.
41 *Nature Nanotechnology*, **2008**, *3*, 563-568. DOI: 10.1038/nnano.2008.215
- 42 [15] M. Khazaei, A. Ranjbar, K. Esfarjani, D. Bogdanovski, R. Dronskowski and S.
43 Yunoki. Insights into exfoliation possibility of MAX phases to MXenes. *Physical*
44 *Chemistry Chemical Physics*, **2018**, *20*, 8579-8592. DOI: 10.1039/C7CP08645H
- 45 [16] E. Er, H.-L. Hou, A. Criado, J. Langer, M. Möller, N. Erk, L. M. Liz-Marzán and
46 M. Prato. High-Yield Preparation of Exfoliated 1T-MoS₂ with SERS Activity. *Chemistry*
47 *of Materials*, **2019**, *31*, 5725-5734. DOI: 10.1021/acs.chemmater.9b01698
- 48 [17] K. C. Knirsch, N. C. Berner, H. C. Nerl, C. S. Cucinotta, Z. Gholamvand, N.
49 McEvoy, Z. Wang, I. Abramovic, P. Vecera, M. Halik, S. Sanvito, G. S. Duesberg, V.
50 Nicolosi, F. Hauke, A. Hirsch, J. N. Coleman and C. Backes. Basal-Plane

1 Functionalization of Chemically Exfoliated Molybdenum Disulfide by Diazonium Salts.
2 *ACS Nano*, **2015**, 9, 6018-6030. DOI: 10.1021/acsnano.5b00965

3 [18] I. Pastoriza-Santos and L. M. Liz-Marzán. Colloidal silver nanoplates. State of
4 the art and future challenges. *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, **2008**, 18, 1724-1737.
5 DOI: 10.1039/B716538B

6 [19] A. C. Kelly, D. O'Suilleabhain, C. Gabbett and J. N. Coleman. The electrical
7 conductivity of solution-processed nanosheet networks. *Nature Reviews Materials*,
8 **2022**, 7, 217-234. DOI: 10.1038/s41578-021-00386-w

9 [20] L. S. van Hazendonk, A. M. Pinto, K. Arapov, N. Pillai, M. R. C. Beurskens, J.-
10 P. Teunissen, A. Sneek, M. Smolander, C. H. A. Rentrop, P. C. P. Bouten and H.
11 Friedrich. Printed Stretchable Graphene Conductors for Wearable Technology.
12 *Chemistry of Materials*, **2022**, 34, 8031-8042. DOI: 10.1021/acs.chemmater.2c02007

13 [21] Z. Gang, Z. Miao, Y. Liu, J. Huang, F. Chen and Q. Fu. High thermal conductivity
14 and increased thickness graphene nanosheet films prepared through metal ion-free
15 route. *Ceramics International*, **2022**, 48, 3711-3719. DOI:
16 10.1016/j.ceramint.2021.10.153

17 [22] X. Zhou, T. Leng, K. Pan, Y. Liu, Z. Zhang, J. Li, K. S. Novoselov and Z. Hu. A
18 sustainable approach towards printed graphene ink for wireless RFID sensing
19 applications. *Carbon*, **2024**, 218, 118693. DOI: 10.1016/j.carbon.2023.118693

20 [23] P. He, Y. Zhang, Z. Wang, P. Min, Z. Deng, L. Li, L. Ye, Z.-Z. Yu and H.-B.
21 Zhang. An energy-saving structural optimization strategy for high-performance
22 multifunctional graphene films. *Carbon*, **2024**, 222, 118932. DOI:
23 10.1016/j.carbon.2024.118932

24 [24] T. Yildirim. The surprising superconductor. *Materials Today*, **2002**, 5, 40-44.
25 DOI: 10.1016/S1369-7021(02)05424-X

26 [25] A. Yousaf, M. S. Gilliam, S. L. Y. Chang, M. Augustin, Y. Guo, F. Tahir, M.
27 Wang, A. Schwindt, X. S. Chu, D. O. Li, S. Kale, A. Debnath, Y. Liu, M. D. Green, E.
28 J. G. Santos, A. A. Green and Q. H. Wang. Exfoliation of Quasi-Two-Dimensional
29 Nanosheets of Metal Diborides. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, **2021**, 125, 6787-
30 6799. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jpcc.1c00394

31 [26] K.-H. Jin, H. Huang, J.-W. Mei, Z. Liu, L.-K. Lim and F. Liu. Topological
32 superconducting phase in high-T_c superconductor MgB₂ with Dirac–nodal-line
33 fermions. *npj Computational Materials*, **2019**, 5, 57. DOI: 10.1038/s41524-019-0191-2

34 [27] I. I. Mazin and V. P. Antropov. Electronic structure, electron–phonon coupling,
35 and multiband effects in MgB₂. *Physica C: Superconductivity*, **2003**, 385, 49-65. DOI:
36 10.1016/S0921-4534(02)02299-2

37 [28] V. P. S. Awana, A. Vajpayee, M. Mudgel, V. Ganesan, A. M. Awasthi, G. L.
38 Bhalla and H. Kishan. Physical property characterization of bulk MgB₂ superconductor.
39 *European Physical Journal B*, **2008**, 62, 281-294. DOI: 10.1140/epjb/e2008-00174-1

40 [29] S. L. Bud'ko and P. C. Canfield. Superconductivity of magnesium diboride.
41 *Physica C-Superconductivity and Its Applications*, **2015**, 514, 142-151. DOI:
42 10.1016/j.physc.2015.02.024

43 [30] J. Nagamatsu, N. Nakagawa, T. Muranaka, Y. Zenitani and J. Akimitsu.
44 Superconductivity at 39 K in magnesium diboride. *Nature*, **2001**, 410, 63-64. DOI:
45 10.1038/35065039

46 [31] A. H. Castro Neto, F. Guinea, N. M. R. Peres, K. S. Novoselov and A. K. Geim.
47 The electronic properties of graphene. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, **2009**, 81, 109-162.
48 DOI: 10.1103/RevModPhys.81.109

49 [32] C. Backes, D. Campi, B. M. Szydłowska, K. Synnatschke, E. Ojala, F.
50 Rashvand, A. Harvey, A. Griffin, Z. Sofer, N. Marzari, J. N. Coleman and D. D.
51 O'Regan. Equipartition of Energy Defines the Size–Thickness Relationship in Liquid-

1 Exfoliated Nanosheets. *ACS Nano*, **2019**, *13*, 7050-7061. DOI:
2 10.1021/acsnano.9b02234

3 [33] M. S. Gilliam, A. Yousaf, Y. Guo, D. O. Li, A. Momenah, Q. H. Wang and A. A.
4 Green. Evaluating the Exfoliation Efficiency of Quasi-2D Metal Diboride Nanosheets
5 Using Hansen Solubility Parameters. *Langmuir*, **2021**, *37*, 1194-1205. DOI:
6 10.1021/acs.langmuir.0c03138

7 [34] R. Patidar, H. Gunda, A. K. Varma, R. Gawas, S. K. Das and K. Jasuja. Co-
8 solvent exfoliation of layered titanium diboride into few-layer-thick nanosheets.
9 *Ceramics International*, **2020**, *46*, 28324-28331. DOI: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2020.07.336

10 [35] S. K. Das and K. Jasuja. Chemical Exfoliation of Layered Magnesium Diboride
11 To Yield Functionalized Nanosheets and Nanoaccordions for Potential Flame
12 Retardant Applications. *ACS Applied Nano Materials*, **2018**, *1*, 1612-1622. DOI:
13 10.1021/acsanm.8b00101

14 [36] S. K. Das, A. Bedar, A. Kannan and K. Jasuja. Aqueous dispersions of few-
15 layer-thick chemically modified magnesium diboride nanosheets by ultrasonication
16 assisted exfoliation. *Scientific Reports*, **2015**, *5*, 10522. DOI: 10.1038/srep10522

17 [37] H. Gunda, S. K. Das and K. Jasuja. Simple, Green, and High-Yield Production
18 of Boron-Based Nanostructures with Diverse Morphologies by Dissolution and
19 Recrystallization of Layered Magnesium Diboride Crystals in Water. *ChemPhysChem*,
20 **2018**, *19*, 880-891. DOI: 10.1002/cphc.201701033

21 [38] Y. Jiang, D. Ka, A. H. Huynh, J. Baek, R. Ning, S.-J. Yu and X. Zheng. Exfoliated
22 Magnesium Diboride (MgB₂) Nanosheets as Solid Fuels. *Nano Letters*, **2023**, *23*,
23 7968-7974. DOI: 10.1021/acs.nanolett.3c01910

24 [39] S. K. Padhi, X. Liu, M. C. Valsania, L. Andreo, A. Agostino, A. Alessio, L.
25 Pastoro, A. Giordana, Z. Wu, G. Cravotto and M. Truccato. Structure and
26 physicochemical properties of MgB₂ nanosheets obtained via sonochemical liquid
27 phase exfoliation. *Nano-Structures & Nano-Objects*, **2023**, *35*, 101016. DOI:
28 10.1016/j.nanoso.2023.101016

29 [40] H. Nishino, T. Fujita, A. Yamamoto, T. Fujimori, A. Fujino, S.-i. Ito, J. Nakamura,
30 H. Hosono and T. Kondo. Formation Mechanism of Boron-Based Nanosheet through
31 the Reaction of MgB₂ with Water. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, **2017**, *121*,
32 10587-10593. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jpcc.7b02348

33 [41] A. L. James and K. Jasuja. Chelation assisted exfoliation of layered borides
34 towards synthesizing boron based nanosheets. *RSC Advances*, **2017**, *7*, 1905-1914.
35 DOI: 10.1039/C6RA26658D

36 [42] D. Ratnam, S. K. Das and K. Jasuja. Ionic Liquid Assisted Exfoliation of Layered
37 Magnesium Diboride. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*,
38 **2017**, *225*, 012111. DOI: 10.1088/1757-899X/225/1/012111

39 [43] R. Muñiz Diaz, P. E. Cardoso-Avila, J. A. Pérez Tavares, R. Patakfalvi, V. Villa
40 Cruz, H. Pérez Ladrón de Guevara, O. Gutiérrez Coronado, R. I. Arteaga Garibay, Q.
41 E. Saavedra Arroyo, V. F. Marañón-Ruiz and J. Castañeda Contreras. Two-Step
42 Triethylamine-Based Synthesis of MgO Nanoparticles and Their Antibacterial Effect
43 against Pathogenic Bacteria. *Nanomaterials*, **2021**, *11*, 410. DOI:
44 10.3390/nano11020410

45 [44] C. Ridings, G. G. Warr and G. G. Andersson. Composition of the outermost
46 layer and concentration depth profiles of ammonium nitrate ionic liquid surfaces.
47 *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, **2012**, *14*, 16088-16095. DOI:
48 10.1039/C2CP43035E

49 [45] P. Nemes-Incze, Z. Osváth, K. Kamarás and L. P. Biró. Anomalies in thickness
50 measurements of graphene and few layer graphite crystals by tapping mode atomic
51 force microscopy. *Carbon*, **2008**, *46*, 1435-1442. DOI: 10.1016/j.carbon.2008.06.022

- 1 [46] K. Nagashio, T. Yamashita, T. Nishimura, K. Kita and A. Toriumi. Electrical
2 transport properties of graphene on SiO₂ with specific surface structures. *Journal of*
3 *Applied Physics*, **2011**, *110*, 024513. DOI: 10.1063/1.3611394
- 4 [47] K. Szendrei, P. Ganter, O. Sánchez-Sobrado, R. Eger, A. Kuhn and B. V.
5 Lotsch. Touchless Optical Finger Motion Tracking Based on 2D Nanosheets with Giant
6 Moisture Responsiveness. *Advanced Materials*, **2015**, *27*, 6341-6348. DOI:
7 10.1002/adma.20150346
- 8 [48] C. Backes, R. J. Smith, N. McEvoy, N. C. Berner, D. McCloskey, H. C. Nerl, A.
9 O'Neill, P. J. King, T. Higgins, D. Hanlon, N. Scheuschner, J. Maultzsch, L. Houben,
10 G. S. Duesberg, J. F. Donegan, V. Nicolosi and J. N. Coleman. Edge and Confinement
11 Effects Allow in situ Measurement of Size and Thickness of Liquid-Exfoliated
12 Nanosheets. *Nature Communications*, **2014**, *5*, 4576. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms5576
- 13 [49] K. Synnatschke, S. Shao, J. van Dinter, Y. J. Hofstetter, D. J. Kelly, S. Grieger,
14 S. J. Haigh, Y. Vaynzof, W. Bensch and C. Backes. Liquid exfoliation of Ni₂P₂S₆:
15 Structural characterisation, size-dependent properties and degradation. *Chemistry of*
16 *Materials*, **2019**, *31*, 9127–9139. DOI: 10.1021/acs.chemmater.9b03468
- 17 [50] C. Gibaja, D. Rodriguez-San-Miguel, P. Ares, J. Gómez-Herrero, M. Varela, R.
18 Gillen, J. Maultzsch, F. Hauke, A. Hirsch, G. Abellán and F. Zamora. Few-Layer
19 Antimonene by Liquid-Phase Exfoliation. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*,
20 **2016**, *55*, 14345-14349. DOI: 10.1002/anie.201605298
- 21 [51] J. Gosch, K. Synnatschke, N. Stock and C. Backes. Comparative study of
22 sonication-assisted liquid phase exfoliation of six layered coordination polymers.
23 *Chemical Communications*, **2023**, *59*, 55-58. DOI: 10.1039/D2CC03366F
- 24 [52] K. Synnatschke, P. A. Cieslik, A. Harvey, A. Castellanos-Gomez, T. Tian, C.-J.
25 Shih, A. Chernikov, E. J. G. Santos, J. N. Coleman and C. Backes. Length and
26 thickness dependent optical response of liquid-exfoliated transition metal
27 dichalcogenides. *Chemistry of Materials*, **2019**, *31*, 10049-10062. DOI:
28 10.1021/acs.chemmater.9b02905
- 29 [53] T. Carey, O. Cassidy, K. Synnatschke, E. Caffrey, J. Garcia, S. Liu, H. Kaur, A.
30 G. Kelly, J. Munuera, C. Gabbett, D. O'Suilleabhain and J. N. Coleman. High-Mobility
31 Flexible Transistors with Low-Temperature Solution-Processed Tungsten
32 Dichalcogenides. *ACS Nano*, **2023**, *17*, 2912-2922. DOI: 10.1021/acsnano.2c11319
- 33 [54] K. Synnatschke. Liquid phase exfoliation and size dependent properties of van
34 der Waals crystals. *Journal*, **2021**. DOI: 10.11588/heidok.00029493
- 35 [55] K. R. Paton, E. Varrla, C. Backes, R. J. Smith, U. Khan, A. O'Neill, C. Boland,
36 M. Lotya, O. M. Istrate, P. King, T. Higgins, S. Barwich, P. May, P. Puczarski, I.
37 Ahmed, M. Moebius, H. Pettersson, E. Long, J. Coelho, S. E. O'Brien, E. K. McGuire,
38 B. M. Sanchez, G. S. Duesberg, N. McEvoy, T. J. Pennycook, C. Downing, A. Crossley,
39 V. Nicolosi and J. N. Coleman. Scalable production of large quantities of defect-free
40 few-layer graphene by shear exfoliation in liquids. *Nature Materials*, **2014**, *13*, 624-
41 630. DOI: 10.1038/nmat3944
- 42 [56] R. Z. Lange, K. Synnatschke, H. Qi, N. Huber, G. Hofer, B. Liang, C. Huck, A.
43 Pucci, U. Kaiser, C. Backes and A. D. Schlüter. Enriching and Quantifying Porous
44 Single Layer 2D Polymers by Exfoliation of Chemically Modified van der Waals
45 Crystals. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, **2020**, *59*, 5683–5695 DOI: 10.1002/anie.201912705
- 46 [57] A. Harvey, C. Backes, J. B. Boland, X. Y. He, A. Griffin, B. Szydłowska, C.
47 Gabbett, J. F. Donegan and J. N. Coleman. Non-resonant light scattering in
48 dispersions of 2D nanosheets. *Nature Communications*, **2018**, *9*. DOI:
49 10.1038/s41467-018-07005-3
- 50 [58] J. Z. Zhang, N. Kong, S. Uzun, A. Levitt, S. Seyedin, P. A. Lynch, S. Qin, M. K.
51 Han, W. R. Yang, J. Q. Liu, X. G. Wang, Y. Gogotsi and J. M. Razal. Scalable

1 Manufacturing of Free-Standing, Strong Ti₃C₂T_x MXene Films with Outstanding
2 Conductivity. *Advanced Materials*, **2020**, 32, 2001093. DOI: 10.1002/adma.202001093
3 [59] A. G. Kelly, J. O'Reilly, C. Gabbett, D. O'Suilleabhain, U. Khan, J. Maughan, T.
4 Carey, S. Sheil, P. Stamenov and J. N. Coleman. Highly Conductive Networks of Silver
5 Nanosheets. *Small*, **2022**, 18, 2105996. DOI: 10.1002/smll.202105996
6 [60] K. Synnatschke, N. Moses Badlyan, A. Wrzesińska, G. Lozano Onrubia, A. L.
7 Hansen, S. Wolff, H. Tornatzky, W. Bensch, Y. Vaynzof, J. Maultzsch and C. Backes.
8 Sonication-assisted liquid phase exfoliation of two-dimensional CrTe₃ under inert
9 conditions. *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry*, **2023**, 98, 106528. DOI:
10 10.1016/j.ultsonch.2023.106528
11 [61] D. Hanlon, C. Backes, E. Doherty, C. S. Cucinotta, N. C. Berner, C. Boland, K.
12 Lee, P. Lynch, Z. Gholamvand, A. Harvey, S. Zhang, K. Wang, G. Moynihan, A. Pokle,
13 Q. M. Ramasse, N. McEvoy, W. J. Blau, J. Wang, G. Abellan, F. Hauke, A. Hirsch, S.
14 Sanvito, D. D. O'Regan, G. S. Duesberg, V. Nicolosi and J. N. Coleman. Liquid
15 Exfoliation of Solvent-Stabilised Few-Layer Black Phosphorus for Applications Beyond
16 Electronics. *Nature Communications*, **2015**, 6, 8563. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms9563
17 [62] G. Abellán, V. Lloret, U. Mundloch, M. Marcia, C. Neiss, A. Görling, M. Varela,
18 F. Hauke and A. Hirsch. Noncovalent Functionalization of Black Phosphorus.
19 *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, **2016**, 55, 14557-14562. DOI:
20 10.1002/anie.201604784
21 [63] H. Arora, Z. Fekri, Y. N. Vekariya, P. Chava, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, M.
22 Helm and A. Erbe. Fully Encapsulated and Stable Black Phosphorus Field-Effect
23 Transistors. *Advanced Materials Technologies*, **2023**, 8, 2200546. DOI:
24 10.1002/admt.202200546
25 [64] W. Huang, Y. Zhang, M. Song, B. Wang, H. Hou, X. Hu, X. Chen and T. Zhai.
26 Encapsulation strategies on 2D materials for field effect transistors and photodetectors.
27 *Chinese Chemical Letters*, **2022**, 33, 2281-2290. DOI: 10.1016/j.ccllet.2021.08.086
28 [65] S. Pinilla, J. Coelho, K. Li, J. Liu and V. Nicolosi. Two-dimensional material inks.
29 *Nature Reviews Materials*, **2022**, 7, 717-735. DOI: 10.1038/s41578-022-00448-7
30 [66] A. L. Window and G. S. Holister. "Strain gauge technology." *Springer Publishing*
31 **1982**, ISBN: 978-0-85334-118-5

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